

D4.3 – Final report on dataset integration

Version 1.3 (Final)

26 August 2022

Grant Agreement number: 823914

Project acronym: ARIADNEplus

Project title: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe - plus

Funding Scheme: H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1

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ARIADNEplus is a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Programme, contract no. H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1-823914. The views and opinions expressed in this presentation are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1) under grant agreement n° 823914.

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Document History

- Version 1.0 – 3 July 2022: First full draft by Achille Felicetti and Julian Richards
- Version 1.1 – 31 July 2022: Contributions from co-authors
- Version 1.2 – 19 August 2022: Submitted for quality control
- Version 1.3 – 26 August 2022: Final version

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes activities carried out within Work Package 4 (WP4) up to Month 44 of the ARIADNEplus project. It describes the outcomes of dataset integration activity (Tasks 4.2 and 4.3) and updates Deliverable D4.1. It also includes an assessment of the support activities carried out in Tasks 4.1 and 4.6, and the digital libraries activity undertaken within Task 4.5. The implementation of the different application profiles carried out in Task 4.4 was reported in D4.2 and will be updated in Deliverable D4.4 at Month 48.

The document is structured according to the activities carried out by WP4. After an overall presentation of the main aims of WP4 in Section 1, Section 2 provides an overview of the AO-Cat conceptual model which was developed in order to facilitate interoperability across the broad range of data resources provided by partners. This was largely reported on in D4.1 but the core features are repeated in this final deliverable for the sake of completeness, and enhancements introduced since Month 18 are highlighted in Section 2.2. Section 2 also presents the fundamental categories defined to classify the information in the Catalogue and make it easily available on the new ARIADNEplus Portal, according to the recommendations of the FAIR principles which inspired the model.

Section 3 presents the dataset integration process, and the principles which have been adopted to maximise interoperability. It describes the pipeline which has been established to support data integration.

Section 4 presents the tools developed and implemented in ARIADNEplus to facilitate data integration according to the AO-Cat model and to assist content providers in all phases of their ingestion, mapping, transformation, enrichment and publication activities. The 3M Mapping Tool developed by FORTH is fundamental as it allows us to define in detail the correspondences between the data provider metadata schemas and the entities of the AO-Cat model, in order to implement an optimal level of integration. The FastCat tool, also developed by FORTH, has been designed for the rapid acquisition of information directly in the AO-Cat model. It has been made available to partners who do not use a pre-defined format for their metadata or who have a limited amount of data to be provided.

Partners must also map their subject vocabularies to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), and the Vocabulary Matching Tool, developed by the University of South Wales (USW), provides a straightforward means of defining matches. It has been implemented as a publicly available ARIADNE Service in D4 Science. Temporal periods are defined using the PeriodO web publishing service which allows us to add From and Until dates in absolute years BCE and AD during the metadata enrichment stage. However, in some cases From and Until dates may already exist in the source metadata, but are often represented in a variety of textual formats. In these cases the USW YearSpans tool is inserted into the workflow to extract numeric values for the From and Until dates. YearSpans automatically performs normalisation based on a wide set of date patterns commonly used in archaeology.

This section also presents Activity Dash, a dashboard system developed by FORTH which allows the aggregation task force to keep track of the multiple workflows, to raise queries, and to provide

feedback to partners. Finally, we report on the use of the Helpdesk, a collaborative service provided within the ARIADNEplus D4 Science platform to assist content providers in all phases of the data contribution and to provide assistance at every stage of the process, from preparation to the definition of mappings, up to fine-tuning the data harvesting and data acquisition mechanisms in the ARIADNEplus infrastructure. The service is based on the ticketing system and offers efficient interaction with the special team of experts set up to provide all the necessary information to foster the process.

Section 5 documents the status of data integration, and shows how partners have adapted their data to the ARIADNEplus standards. We are able to report outstanding success in achieving a critical mass of high-quality archaeological data resources, available for research under an open licence, and easily discoverable via the ARIADNE portal, which represents a powerful research tool in its own right. As this Deliverable is submitted, we have over three million resources integrated in the portal, and anticipate that by Month 48 that figure will be closer to four million. The current resources derive from over 30 partner data providers (or “Publishers”) from as many countries, and covering three continents. We anticipate that by Month 48 over 40 data providers will be represented. Most significantly this includes data from over ten Associate Partners who have asked to supply data at their own expense, but with support of the ARIADNE Aggregation Task Force. These include the existing specialist multinational aggregation services ROCEEH and THANADOS.¹ There is a clear appreciation of the importance of ARIADNE amongst the world archaeological community and an appetite from those beyond the original project partnership to make their data sets available via the ARIADNE platform.

Section 6 presents the activities aimed at linking the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure with repositories of scientific publications, exploiting, in particular, OpenAIRE and its open access digital archives and the links to individual journals such as Internet Archaeology. The gateway for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, whose features have been updated and improved, is also presented. In addition, we outline the methodologies used by the ARIADNEplus text mining service and the results produced by its relational citation matching algorithm, used to improve the metadata generation of relevant textual resources and dynamically link them to the ARIADNEplus ecosystem.

Finally, the conclusions and an evaluation of the activities carried out in the project are presented in Section 7, along with plans for sustainability of data integration activities. ARIADNEplus has been outstandingly successful in bringing together a much broader range of records than the predecessor ARIADNE project, upon whose success it has been able to build. The intention was to integrate datasets ranging widely in space and time, and across a wider range of archaeological sub-domains. All these ambitions have been achieved. At Month 44 we have over 1120 resources which pre-date 1,000,000 BP, and 62,723 resources which post-date AD 1900, demonstrating the full range of 21st century archaeological research. We have resources from North and South America, Europe and Scandinavia, and Asia. The integrated data covers every ARIADNE resource type, from inscriptions and rock art to scientific analyses and dating resources. We have integrated over one million records for

¹ https://www.roceeh.uni-tuebingen.de/roadweb/smarty_road_simple_search.php
<https://thanados.net>

individual sites and monuments, over 500,000 artefacts and over 450,000 coins. Our catalogue includes over 250,000 unpublished fieldwork reports, and over 100,000 full fieldwork archives. This is the first time that many of these resources have been brought together, making it possible to address some of the grand challenges of archaeology. In addition, the data integration approach and supporting infrastructure have proved their value and extensibility for use in other contexts, at national, regional or thematic level, allowing the same data resources to be presented in multiple showcases. In summary, what has been achieved in ARIADNEplus represents a massive digital research infrastructure now available freely and easily as Open Access data to European scientists and researchers, teachers and students, as well as to interested members of the public.

1 Introduction and Objectives

The main objective of Work Package 4 (WP4) is to foster the integration of datasets from the ARIADNEplus archaeological research community. ARIADNEplus aims to integrate the best and most important research infrastructures within the archaeological domain and provide services for effective access and re-use of data.

The consortium has defined a data model which is directly based upon the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM). The CIDOC CRM is a formal ontology in the form of a semantic model, i.e. it declares each attribute value as an a priori independent entity in the universe of discourse and connects such values symmetrically by directed links/arcs/properties. The CIDOC CRM has gained the support of a large portion of the Cultural Heritage domain, as witnessed for example by its influence on the Europeana Data Model.

The ARIADNE Data Model, the AO-Cat, inherits the CIDOC CRM model and philosophy to provide the community with a powerful and efficient integration tool, capable of capturing the meaning of a diverse range of archaeological data sets offered by content providers and integrating their data in a unique and coherent way. However, it also focuses on a limited subset of the CRM properties, making it more accessible to archaeological data providers.

WP4 activities are focused on facilitating the adoption of the ARIADNEplus AO-Cat data model within the consortium by means of recommendations, advice and tools aimed to simplify the conversion of data and their integration in a standard format. According to these objectives, WP4 deploys a series of strategies aimed at implementing and strengthening data integration and interoperability, that mainly focus on:

1. Creating and offering services to support users in contributing to the ARIADNEplus integration objective.
2. Providing guidelines and tools to integrate datasets and data in the ARIADNEplus archaeological Data Infrastructure.
3. Support users in mapping and/or conversion of their archaeological metadata and datasets to the ARIADNEplus standards.
4. Facilitate the integration of archaeological data into the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base (previously described as Content Cloud).

This Deliverable reports on activities undertaken to the end of Month 44 of the ARIADNEplus project. It describes the outcomes of dataset integration activity (Tasks 4.2 and 4.3) and updates Deliverable D4.1. It also includes an assessment of the support activities carried out in Tasks 4.1 and 4.6, and the digital libraries activity undertaken within Task 4.5. The implementation of the different application profiles carried out in Task 4.4 was reported in D4.2 and will be updated in Deliverable D4.4 at Month 48.

The document is structured according to the activities carried out by WP4. After an overall presentation of the main aims of WP4 in Section 1, Section 2 provides an overview of the AO-Cat conceptual model which was developed in order to facilitate interoperability across the broad range

of data resources provided by partners. This was largely reported on D4.1 but the core features are repeated in this final deliverable for the sake of completeness, and enhancements introduced since Month 18 are highlighted in Section 2.2. Section 2 also presents the fundamental categories defined to classify the information in the Catalogue and make it easily available on the new ARIADNEplus Portal, according to the recommendations of the FAIR principles which inspired the model.

Section 3 presents the dataset integration process, and the principles which have been adopted to maximise interoperability. It describes the pipeline which has been established to support data integration.

Section 4 presents the tools developed and implemented in ARIADNEplus to facilitate data integration according to the AO-Cat model and to assist content providers in all phases of their ingestion, mapping, transformation, enrichment and publication activities.

Section 5 documents the status of data integration, and shows how partners have adapted their data to the ARIADNEplus standards.

Section 6 presents the activities aimed at linking the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure with repositories of scientific publications, exploiting, in particular, OpenAire and its open access digital archives and the links to individual journals such as Internet Archaeology. This section also describes the use of the ARIADNEplus text mining service to improve the metadata for the textual resources.

Finally, the conclusions and an evaluation of the activities carried out in the project are presented in Section 7, along with plans for sustainability of data integration activities.

2 The ARIADNEplus Data Model

2.1 AO-Cat Ontology for the ARIADNE Catalogue

The AO-Cat Ontology (AO-Cat for short) is a formal ontology of the resources catalogued by ARIADNE. Its tight relation with the CIDOC-CRM ensures compatibility with wider data aggregation infrastructures. The aim of the AO-Cat is to present a core ontology to which data providers map their individual database schema, thereby ensuring interoperability between diverse resources. It is capable of being deployed at the “site” or “monument” level, but we have demonstrated that it can also be effectively implemented at item level, e.g. for individual artefacts or graves, providing a much more granular level of interoperability. ARIADNEplus resource types can be used in the portal to filter at different levels. Further specialisations for specific resources types, or “application profiles” have been developed under subtask 4.4 (reported in deliverable D4.2, with an update in final deliverable D4.4)

2.1.1 Requirements

There are two basic requirements of the AO-Cat:

1. Enabling cross-institution resource discovery, i.e. *finding* data.
2. Enabling interoperability across partners, data types, data schemas, i.e. *enabling research*.

For resource discovery, the ARIADNE Knowledge Base should support:

- *What* searches: searches based on a subject topic. To describe the subject(s) of a resource consistently, the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus should be used as the common conceptual backbone, in addition to local reference resources.
- *When* searches: searches based on a temporal period. For temporal periods, the PeriodO vocabulary should be used as it maps periods to absolute dates on a common time scale. In addition, local vocabularies providing region-related period appellations should be represented in ARIADNE to permit searches by cultural period e.g. “Iron Age”²
- *Where* searches: searches based on a spatial region. For spatial regions, the World Geodetic System 1984 (commonly abbreviated as WGS84) representation should be used. As this is latitude longitude based it avoids the limitations of specific national grid reference systems. ARIADNE supports enhanced map-based searching, including polygon searching.

In order to enable research, in addition to the above types of search, ARIADNE catalogues information about digital objects belonging to a large range of data types, forming a heterogeneous set, as data is diverse in character and content. These data types include, but are not restricted to:

² <https://periodo.do/en/>

- Databases
- Reports
- Finds
- Images
- GIS
- LiDAR data
- Datasets e.g. excavation archives
- Sub-domains, e.g. scientific data

In addition, different levels of granularity must be accounted for, supporting collection and item level interoperability, e.g. archaeological sites and the individual artefacts they contain.

Moreover, links to distributed digital and paper resources about the described resources should be maintained. Sources of datasets and rights management and access issues also need to be transparently recorded.

The AO-Cat has been already introduced in detail in deliverable D4.1. This section will therefore summarise its key points.

2.1.2 The AO-Cat namespace

ARIADNE has defined a new namespace for the AO-Cat classes and properties as opposed to re-using the namespace of the existing CIDOC CRM ontology so as to be able to define freely the classes and properties needed to match the project requirements, although all classes and properties have been mapped to the CRM. Those familiar with the Dublin Core metadata scheme will also observe that AO-Cat can be directly mapped to Dublin Core and therefore it also reflects a qualified Dublin Core schema.

2.1.3 ARIADNE Resources

The most general resource class in ARIADNE is `AO_Data_Resource`, representing all the digital resources the ARIADNE infrastructure deals with.³

There are a few properties that apply to all data resources:

- `has_type`, a type of the resource in any classification system.
- `has_title`, a title of the resource.
- `has_description`, a textual description of the resource.

³ It should be noted that the full AO-Cat also includes higher level entities as ARIADNE also catalogues data services as well as data resources, but the scope of this document is limited to data sets so these have not been included.

Figure 1: Resource class hierarchy for data resources. AO_Digital_Image is an addition to AO-Cat - see section 2.2.2

The rest of this Section gives some fundamental principles that AO-Cat follows in describing data resources.

2.1.4 Resource identification

An ARIADNE resource is a web resource; therefore it is identified by an HTTPS IRI in the ARIADNE domain. The identifier of the resource in this namespace is called the “primary” resource identifier and is computed at aggregation time from the local identifier of the resource.

In addition to the primary identifier, the UC also represents the identifier of the resource in the namespace of the data provider. This identifier, which is called the “local” resource identifier, is associated with the resource via the property ‘has_original_id’, which has simple character strings as values, to allow maximum generality. It is understood that the local identifier of a resource is the identifier used by the publisher of the resource, which is the Agent making the resource publicly available (see below). Finally, ARIADNE also allows the representation of other identifiers of a resource than the one in the publisher namespace, via the property ‘has_identifier’. This property ranges over character strings for generality. As a consequence, it is not possible to represent any additional knowledge about these other identifiers other than the knowledge that can be inferred from the identifiers themselves.

2.1.5 Resource description

A number of descriptive properties are defined for an ARIADNE data resource. AO-Cat treats these data types simply as tags because no specific property is defined for a specific data type.

Dates:

- `was_issued`, the date when the record of the resource was first made available online.
- `was_modified`, the date when the record of the resource was last modified.
Initially, at least, these may each take the same value.
- `was_created_on`, the date in which the resource was created, which may be earlier than when it was first made available online.

People, or 'agents':

- `has_publisher`, the agent responsible for making the resource accessible online e.g. the Archaeology Data Service.
- `has_contributor`, a contributor of a description of the resource, e.g. Historic England
- `has_creator`, the original creator of the resource, e.g. Mortimer Wheeler
- `has_owner`, the owner of the resource e.g. National Institute of Archaeology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
- `has_responsible`, any person who is scientifically responsible for the resource e.g. Agatha Christie

In some cases, one or more of these may all be the same person or organisation.

Agents play important roles in the ARIADNE information space: they are responsible for making resources available and publicly accessible; they hold various types of responsibilities for those resources; finally, they carry out activities. For these reasons, AO-Cat defines the class Agent to model entities that can act.

Moreover, from an archaeological perspective it is important to distinguish between two kinds of agents: the person and the organisation: Julian Richards as the individual and researcher and/or excavation director (who might have an ORCID or other id) and University of York as the organisation that was legally responsible for the excavation or its funding, or publication etc. This distinction is captured in AO-Cat by two subclasses of Agent:

- Person, modelling individual humans, and
- Group, modelling "gatherings or organisations of agents that act collectively or in a similar way due to any form of unifying relationship" [CRM Spec 6.2].

The following properties are defined on instances of Agent, regardless whether the agent is a person or a group:

- `has_name`, giving the name of the agent.
- `has_agent_identifier`, giving any identifier of an agent outside of the ARIADNE namespace.
- `has_homepage`, giving a web page for the agent.

- `has_institution`, giving the institution(s) of the agent.

For the Agent ‘`has_publisher`’ (usually the data provider to ARIADNE) we retain the additional property:

- `has_email`, giving the email address of the organisation

(This has been removed for individuals to avoid any potential breach of GDPR).

Finally, we need to provide additional administrative information about data resources, including the language of the resource, and other information to guide users on what they can do with the resource:

- `has_language`, the language of the resource.
- `has_landing_page`, the original landing page of the `AO_Data_Resource`, if any.
- `has_access_policy`, a statement of access policy for the resource.
- `has_access_rights`, a statement of access rights on the resource.
- `has_extent`, the size of the resource.

2.1.6 Resource subject matter

Data resources are also characterised in terms of the entity they are about. The connection between a data resource and the entity the resource is about is captured by property `refers_to`:

- `refers_to` associates a data resource with an entity that the resource refers to, by making assertions, whether implicitly or explicitly and regardless of the format, about that entity.

As a special case of reference, there is also the property `is_about`:

- `is_about` associates a data resource with the primary entity that the data resource documents, including of course events. Notice that the documenting data resource may be an external resource, identified by an IRI, or DOI, or any other identifier, to capture the requirement that ARIADNE should have links to distributed digital and paper resources.

In turn, `is_about` is categorised into three sub-properties making it possible to trace the provenance of the association between the data resource and entity it is about:

- `has_native_subject` models the association directly imported from the provider of the data. Ideally, this should normally be a MIDAS term, defined and allocated a URI at heritagedata.org
- `has_derived_subject` models the association computed by the aggregator by mapping the native subject to an AAT term, to match the requirement that “the Getty AAT should be used as the common conceptual backbone, in addition to local reference resources”.
- `has_ARIADNE_subject` models the association between the data resource and one of the fundamental ARIADNE resource types. The list of ARIADNE fundamental resource types is a pragmatic classification, which was defined “bottom-up” according to the types of data supplied by partners. In the ARIADNE portal it allows searches to be filtered according to different levels of granularity e.g., artefact vs site/monument. Each `ARIADNE_Subject` has a

unique icon and a short name displayed in the ARIADNE portal. The same ARIADNE_Subject and its related icon are used for the collection and individual data resources, e.g., a database of burials will have the same subject/icon as an individual burial record within it.

The full list of ARIADNE_Subjects is:

- Site/monument
- Fieldwork
- Fieldwork report
- Fieldwork archive
- Scientific analysis
- Date
- Artefact
- Coin
- Building survey
- Maritime
- Inscription
- Rock Art
- Burial

Although the AO-Cat allows the specification of several ARIADNE_Subjects for a resource, we have encouraged partners to choose the most appropriate (at the most detailed or granular level available) to maximise the value of this category for filtering purposes in the portal.

2.1.7 Concept matching

AO-Cat provides the class AO_Concept to represent topics in each category. Moreover, to allow providers to associate the necessary information with each concept, AO_Concept is declared equivalent to skos:Concept. As a consequence, all properties defined by SKOS on concepts can be applied to any instance of AO_Concept. For instance:

- the properties skos:broader and skos:narrower can be used to model concept taxonomies;
- the properties skos:broadMatch, skos:closeMatch, skos:exactMatch, skos:narrowMatch, skos:relatedMatch can be used to specify the kind of mapping leading to the instance of the concept;
- the property skos:inScheme can be used to specify the ontology or the terminology where a concept comes from.

The reason why it has been decided to re-use SKOS (as opposed to define the above properties in AO-Cat) is that SKOS is by now a *de facto* standard, thoroughly tested in many years of application in a wide range of contexts; so, there is no reason to doubt that SKOS will not be adequate to the needs of ARIADNE in concept modelling.

The taxonomy of aboutness properties is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Taxonomy of “aboutness” properties in AO-Cat

2.1.8 Spatial regions

In addition to subject matter, required to support *What* searches, the requirements highlight the importance of spatial coverage, required to support *Where* searches. To account for this aspect, AO-Cat uses the property ‘has_spatial_coverage’, associating an instance of AO_Data_Resource with a spatial region. The generic AO-Cat class for spatial regions is AO_Spatial_Region. Three properties are defined for the instances of this class:

- has_coordinate_system
- has_place_name
- has_country_code

Four main representations of a spatial region are provided by AO-Cat, each assigned to a specific subclass of AO_Spatial_Region. These subclasses are (see Figure 3 below):

- AO_Spatial_Region_Point, having as instances regions that are points. The properties defined on points are:
 - has_latitude
 - has_longitude

- AO_Spatial_Region_Polygon, having as instances regions that are polygons, represented in some format typically managed by a GIS. No commitment is made by AO-Cat on a specific notation for these regions, they are treated simply as abstract objects with a specific property:
 - has_polygonal_representation
giving the XML document representing the polygonal region.

- AO_Spatial_Region_BBox, having as instances regions that are bounded boxes, represented by four points giving the vertices of the box. The properties defined on points are:
 - has_bounding_box_min_lat
 - has_bounding_box_min_lon
 - has_bounding_box_max_lat
 - has_bounding_box_max_lon

- AO_Spatial_Region_StdName having as instances regions that are simply identified by a standard name in some vocabulary. The standard name is given by the property:
 - has_place_IRI

Figure 3: Spatial Region and its subclasses

2.1.9 Temporal regions

In addition to *What* and *Where* searches, the requirements also highlight the importance of temporal coverage, in order to support *When* searches. To account for this aspect AO-Cat introduces the property ‘has_temporal_coverage’, associating an instance of AO_Data_Resource with a temporal region.

Time is represented and named in many different ways in the archaeological domain, often inextricably associated with space. Fortunately, reference resources have been created in the last decade, which make the task of accounting for time much easier for ARIADNE.

According to the requirements, AO-Cat should support both time points, defined as absolute dates with respect to a reference system, and time intervals, defined as temporal extents having a beginning, an end and a non-zero duration. In addition, time intervals identified by names (e.g.,

“*Neolithic*”) should be supported, whether these names are drawn from a standard or a local vocabulary.

For the representation of time points, AO-Cat relies on the “date” data type of the XML Schema type system, written as `xsd:date`.

For the representation of time intervals and their names, AO-Cat relies on the PeriodO service which makes it possible to define a temporal interval as a web resource, associated with a label and two absolute dates giving the earliest start and the latest stop of the interval. The service also makes it possible to cluster period resources in collections, thus facilitating the exploration of the gazetteer data space.

The AO-Cat class `AO_Temporal_Region` has time intervals as instances. Each such instance can be described by means of the following four properties:

- `has_period`, giving the PeriodO time interval as an IRI.
- `has_native_period`, giving the local identifier of the period, as an instance of `AO_Concept`.
- `from`, giving the beginning of the interval as an (RDF literal of type) `xsd:date`.
- `until`, giving the end of the interval as an (RDF literal of type) `xsd:date`.

2.2 Updates to the AO-Cat Ontology since Month 18

The AO-Cat has always been regarded as a living document which has evolved as archaeological requirements have been refined in the light of data provided for integration. Minor changes and corrections have been made since its inception and these are identified in the document history. There have been three major additions since Deliverable D4.1: the capacity to indicate spatial precision, the facility to add images, and the requirement to add a country name as part of describing the spatial coverage of a resource.

2.2.1 Spatial Precision

After the first 18 months it became clear that some data providers wished to accompany the information on the spatial region covered by a data resource by a further specification of precision.

This may be due to several reasons, such as:

- The data provider has sensitive spatial data which they do not wish to make publicly available, maybe to protect the precise location of a site. Therefore, they should only supply to ARIADNE the data at a resolution which they are willing to make publicly available, e.g. for the UK Portable Antiquities Scheme this is the parish administrative unit, and we would then use GeoNames to provide a centroid point for the parish.
- The data provider may only hold data for site location at an imprecise level, so we need to make it clear when we plot locations on a map, that the point represents the site location to the nearest, e.g. 10 km.

In order to cope with these and with similar cases, we introduced a property:

- `has_spatial_precision`

associating a data resource with a specification of the precision that characterises the spatial coverage of the resource. Note that a resource may cover at most one spatial region, therefore such precision specification can always unambiguously be referred to the appropriate region.

As to the range of property ‘`has_spatial_precision`’, we observe that some providers are able to say exactly how accurate the points they supply are, while others are only able to give a qualitative assessment. On balance it has been decided to allow providers to give a quantitative specification, for three reasons:

1. Whenever that information is available, the AO-Cat makes it possible to represent it.
2. A quantitative specification will be very useful when displaying the points on a map.
3. A quantitative specification will avoid creating a special vocabulary for a qualitative specification, such as “high” “medium” “low”.

For the specification of quantitative information, we thus introduce class `AO_Dimension`, a subclass of `crm:E54 Dimension`, as the range of property ‘`has_spatial_dimension`’. There are two properties that have `AO_Dimension` as domain:

- `has_value`, sub-property of `crm:P90 has value`, for associating a numeric value with the specification, range is `rdfs:Literal`
- `has_unit`, sub-property of `P91 has unit`, for associating a unit of measurement with the specification, range is `AO_Concept`.

In addition to these properties, property ‘`has_type`’ can be used for associating a type with the specification.

2.2.2 Digital Images

Since Deliverable D4.1 it has also become clear that there would be an additional benefit to be able to use the ARIADNE Portal to display one or more images (generally thumbnails) along with the textual metadata about a resource. Any kind of resource can have associated thumbnails. In particular:

- an individual data resource can have thumbnails portraying the resource it is about (e.g. the recto and verso of a coin);
- a collection data resource can have thumbnails relative to any subset of the items it contains;
- the thumbnails associated with a service can be, for instance, the logo of the service.

Amongst the provided thumbnails, providers would also like to have the possibility of indicating a *primary* image, to be used wherever a single image needs to be selected for the record (for instance, in a search result). The following conditions were agreed:

- The displayed thumbnails must be web resources on the provider’s site, i.e. they must be identified by a local URI and accessible through that URI on the provider’s site.

- Providers are given the option of copying the thumbnails to be displayed into the AC (for a fixed maximum size), or keeping these thumbnails exclusively in their own storage, to be pulled at display time by the Portal software. The latter solution is encouraged, to avoid the problem of storing too many images in the AC, and the consequent copyright or update problems.
- Each thumbnail copied into the ARIADNE Content Cloud is given a URI on the ARIADNE namespace; that URI must be associated with the link to the original thumbnail on the provider's site for reference.
- Each thumbnail copied into the ARIADNE Content Cloud must be licensed under a CC0 licence by the provider.
- In order to mitigate the problem of broken links, the portal does not display the thumbnail for a broken link

To accommodate these requirements AO-Cat was modified so that each digital image is an instance of class `AO_Digital_Image`, a new class that is added to AO-Cat for the purpose of modelling thumbnails and other digital images in the AC. `AO_Digital_Image` is a direct sub-class of `AO_Individual_Data_Resource` and of `crm:E90 Symbolic Object`.

Property `'is_mirror_of'` is used to associate a digital image in the AC with the image it is a copy of on the provider's site. The domain of this property is `AO_Digital_Image` while its range is `rdfs:Resource`; the property is not mandatory, but it is functional so that a digital image is the mirror of at most one image. This property is a sub-property of `owl:sameAs` and a shortcut of the more developed path in the CRM involving class `E91 Co-Reference Assignment` and property `P155 has co-reference target`.

Property `'has_visual_component'`, having `AO_Resource` as domain and `AO_Digital_Image` as range, is defined to associate a resource with a digital image that is part of the resource and that provides some visual information about it. The property is not mandatory and no cardinality constraint is defined on it, so that a resource can have zero, one, or more digital images as visual components. The property is a sub-property of `crm:P106 'is composed of'`. In order to let data providers select a *primary* image to be associated with the resource, a special property is defined, named `'has_primary_visual_component'`, a sub-property of `'has_visual_component'` having the same domain and the same range and, in addition, being functional (i.e., a record can have at most one primary image).

The diagram below illustrates the model for images that are copied into the AC, using a coin in the DIME database (<https://www.metaldetektorfund.dk/fund/?dimeid=106900>) as an example. In the diagram:

- classes are in light blue, while arcs are labelled by the property corresponding to their colours, given in the bottom part of the figure
- `ai:idr_106900` is an individual data resource, namely a record provided by the project DIME for sharing through the ARIADNE infrastructure. In the AC, this resource:
 - refers to the coin `ai:coin_106900`, an instance of `AO_Object`;
 - has the digital images `ai:di_1` to `ai:di_4` as visual components; these images are the same as the DIME resources `dime_1` to `dime_4`, respectively;

- the actual images are obtained via de-referentiation of the corresponding URIs by the appropriate web server, either on the ARIADNE infrastructure (for the URIs of the form ai:di_n) or on the DIME project site (for the URIs of the form dime_n).

Figure 4: The data model for images that are copied into the ARIADNE knowledge base

Whenever the record is modified on the DIME site, for instance by replacing one or more of the 4 images (`dime_i`) with different images identified by different URIs, that record must be re-aggregated. The same must be done if any one of the four images is modified on the DIME site but the URIs that identify the modified images remain the same, because the image associated with the URI is copied into the AC.

For generality, the model does not make any assumption about the relationships between the images that are part of the record (`ai:di_1` to `ai:di_4` in the example) and the object (`ai:coin_106900`) that the record refers to. If desired, such relationships can be asserted as additional information. In the above example, in CRM terms any one of the four images that are the content of the digital images `ai:di_j` is a visual representation of the coin; this can be asserted by using property *P138 represents* between the coin and the content of each digital image. Such level of detail is not necessary to capture the requirements stated above, therefore the classes and properties for representing this information are not part of the present model.

The following diagram illustrates the model for images that are **not** copied into the AC. For perspicuity, the same object as the one used in the previous diagram is used, assuming the corresponding thumbnails are not copied into the AC:

Figure 5: The data model for images that are not copied into the ARIADNE knowledge base

The main difference is that the four images are not part of the AC, they are just referred to in statements, where they are identified using the URIs of the providers.

2.2.3 Country

Finally, during the course of data integration it also became clear that there was a user requirement to be able to filter results by country. This had not been a major issue at M18 as the majority of data providers only published resources from within their own country. However, as the project increasingly cooperated with existing multinational aggregators, such as ROCEEH for palaeolithic archaeology, and THANADOS for early mediaeval burials, this became more difficult. Country was not coincidentally coded as a place name and so it was decided to add it as a distinct property in AO-Cat.

Property 'has_country_code' was therefore added as a mandatory property of AO_Spatial_Region.

The property takes the Wikipedia IRI corresponding to the 3-letter alphabetic code set by ISO 3166 country code where a spatial region belongs. For example, the spatial region W belonging to Afghanistan has code https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-3#AFG

To avoid having to go back to data providers and reload existing data, it was possible for CNR to use Geo-Services VRE in D4Science to retrospectively add 'has_county_code' to all existing records.

3 Mapping the ARIADNEplus Data Model

3.1 Data Mapping

The integrated metadata is searchable via the ARIADNEplus portal according to three main facets: Where (place) / When (time) / What (subject). To support effective cross-search of metadata originating from many different countries requires some shared common understanding of the meaning of the metadata. The “where” and “when” facets may be communicated using common data types and comparable values (e.g. spatial coordinates relative to a known location on the earth, date ranges relative to a known epoch). The “what” (subject) aspect can be more difficult to define in a commonly understood and comparable format.

Clean and consistent metadata is a prerequisite for effective integration and reuse, as we can neither predict nor dictate the way in which it may be reused in the future. Inconsistent or erroneous metadata causes problems in accurately identifying co-references or mappings. Embedded errors may resurface and be magnified where the metadata is subsequently reused in a different context, causing difficulties in performing logical reasoning – and leading to potentially inaccurate assertions or conclusions in future studies.

3.1.1 Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus

The Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) provides concepts and terms to describe cultural heritage concepts. The AAT is made available as Linked Open Data (LOD)⁴, so each concept in the thesaurus has a unique identifier in the form of a URI (e.g. <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300211545> is the identifier of the concept "*penannular brooches*"). ARIADNEplus is using AAT as a central hub for scalable interconnection of local subject vocabularies. Data providers are required to provide a set of mappings from their own local subject vocabulary (all terms used to describe subjects in their own metadata) to the AAT. The aim of the subject mapping exercise is to improve recall and precision when later browsing and searching the ARIADNEplus integrated data by subject (time and space are being handled separately).

Mappings are inherently reusable as they describe semantic relationships between persistent concepts relating to the domain, but are not restricted in scope to any particular dataset. Therefore, ARIADNEplus has been able to re-use subject mappings already produced in the previous ARIADNE project, although many have been extended and revised. For example, for the UK we have refined mappings so that they are specific to the constituent countries (England, Scotland, Northern Ireland) and also added more granularity for maritime terms.

⁴ vocab.getty.edu

The screenshot shows the Getty AAT landing page for the concept 'penannular brooches'. The page header includes the logo and navigation options: 'Getty Vocabularies: LOD', 'SPARQL', 'Queries', 'AAT', 'Search...', 'Search', and 'Brief'. The main title is 'penannular brooches' with the source URL 'http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300211545'. Below the title are tabs for 'Subject (49)', 'Predicate', 'Object', and 'All'. There are also links for 'Website', 'Hierarchy', and 'Download in: JSON | JSONLD | RDF | N3/Turtle | N-Triples'. An 'Inference' dropdown menu is set to 'Explicit only'. The main content area is titled 'Statements in which the resource exists as a subject.' and contains a table with the following data:

Predicate	Object
rdf:type	gvp:Concept
rdfs:seeAlso	http://www.getty.edu/vow/AATFullDisplay?find=&logic=AND&note=&subjectid=300211545
dcterms:created	1992-03-05T00:00:00
dcterms:modified	2001-07-26T22:03:06, 2010-04-23T05:52:09, 2010-04-23T05:52:10, 2012-03-14T15:05:29, 2012-03-16T14:11:48, 2014-12-05T08:40:23, 2014-12-05T08:43:10
skos:changeNote	aat_rev:5000052642, aat_rev:5001133770, aat_rev:5001133771, aat_rev:5001133772, aat_rev:5002479845, aat_rev:5002479851, aat_rev:5003174190, aat_rev:5003174193, aat_rev:5003178253, aat_rev:5003763847, aat_rev:5003763848, aat_rev:5003765784
gvp:parentString	brooches, pins (jewelry), jewelry worn on costume, <jewelry by location>, jewelry, worn costume accessories, costume accessories, costume (mode of fashion), Costume (hierarchy name), Furnishings and Equipment (hierarchy name), Objects Facet
gvp:parentStringAbbrev	brooches, pins (jewelry), ... Objects Facet
gvp:displayOrder	2
xl:prefLabel	aat_term:1000211545-en, aat_term:1000538040-es, aat_term:1000611650-nl
xl:altLabel	aat_term:1000226276-en, aat_term:1000294365-en, aat_term:1000447710-es, aat_term:1000611651-nl
gvp:broaderGeneric	aat:300045995
gvp:broaderPreferred	aat:300045995
gvp:prefLabelGVP	aat_term:1000211545-en
skos:inScheme	aat
skos:scopeNote	aat_scopeNote:124494, aat_scopeNote:36428, aat_scopeNote:75533
dcterms:contributor	aat_contrib:10000000, aat_contrib:10000088, aat_contrib:10000131
dcterms:source	aat_source:200005951-subject-300211545, aat_source:2000051089-subject-300211545
dc:identifier	300211545
dcterms:license	http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/by/1.0/
cc:license	http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/by/1.0/
void:inDataset	http://vocab.getty.edu/dataset/aat
prov:wasGeneratedBy	aat_rev:5000052642

Figure 6: Example of a Getty AAT landing page for a URI concept, in this case for 'penannular brooches'

3.1.2 PeriodO

PeriodO⁵ is a multilingual gazetteer of period definitions for describing historical and archaeological named periods. It comprises a series of 'authorities' (lists of named periods) where each individual period definition is associated with a particular geographical area and a start date and end date. Periods and authorities have 'permalink' identifiers (URIs) so they can be clearly and unambiguously referenced - e.g. the identifier <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0rrjd9gix9> defines the period "Moyen Âge" (Middle Ages) within the authority <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0rrjd9> "INRAP: Chronologie Generale. 2007". All named periods in ARIADNEplus have been defined with reference to periods within PeriodO. This has generally necessitated creating and submitting a new authority via the PeriodO client application, however for organisations which participated in the first ARIADNE project existing PeriodO authorities were re-used. All dates provided, either via PeriodO or as dates already expressed

⁵ <https://perio.do/en/>

in absolute years in partner’s datasets, are expressed in years Common Era (CE) i.e. 2020 CE or AD 2020, or 400 BCE or 400 BC. If partners hold data in years BP (using either 1950 or 2000 as present) it is required that this is first transformed to years CE.

PeriodO

Home
[Data sources](#)
[Settings](#)
[About](#)

Data source
[Browse periods](#)
[Browse authorities](#)
[Review submitted changes](#)
[History](#)
[Settings](#)

Authority
[View](#)
[History](#)

Period
[View](#)
[History](#)

Canonical > INRAP: Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventive. PACTOLS chronology periods used... > Chronologie américaine > View

Chronologie américaine

-23000 – 1492 | France

Defined by INRAP: Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventive. PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data. 2021.

Permalink <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr43h3c>

Download [JSON](#), [Turtle](#)

|| *Employer ce terme pour les périodes entre la préhistoire et l'arrivée des Espagnols (BL)*

▼ **Period details**

	Label	Start ▼	Stop	Spatial coverage	Pub. date
14	view Préhistoire	-800000	-3001	France	2021
15	view Pléistocène moyen	-779000	-124001	France	2021
16	view Paléolithique moyen	-300000	-40001	France	2021
17	view Pléistocène supérieur	-124000	-9701	France	2021
18	view Paléolithique supérieur	-40000	-12501	France	2021
19	view Chronologie américaine	-23000	1492	France	2021
20	view Bölling	-13000	-12101	France	2021
21	view FinalAnlithique et Méso	-12500	-5501	France	2021

Authority [view](#)

Permalink
<http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4>

Source

Title
PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data

Creators
INRAP: Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventive

Citation
PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data

Year published
2021

Web page
<https://pactols.frantiq.fr/>

Editorial notes
This is a subset of terms originating from the 'périodisation' hierarchy of PACTOLS thesaurus of the Frantiq network, representing terms frequently used in DOLIA data. For the full hierarchy see <https://pactols.frantiq.fr/>
This data is supplemented with dates supplied by INRAP for use in the ARIADNEplus project

Download
[JSON](#), [Turtle](#), [CSV](#)

Period [view](#)

Permalink
<http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr43h3c>

Original label
Chronologie américaine

Start
-23000 -23000

Stop
1492 1492

Spatial coverage
France [wikidata:France](#)

Language
French

Alternate labels
New World Chronology *English*
Altamerikanische Kulturen *German*
Amerikaanse chronologie *Dutch*
Cronologia amerindia *Spanish*
Cronologia amerindiana *Italian*
التسلسل الزمني للثقافات الهندوأمريكية *Arabic*
Chronologie américaine *French*

Notes from source
Employer ce terme pour les périodes entre la préhistoire et l'arrivée des Espagnols (BL)

Web page
<https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pct9hLpUyQcym>

Download
[JSON](#), [Turtle](#)

Figure 7: PeriodO: period definitions for France provided by Inrap

The purpose of using PeriodO in ARIADNEplus is different to the use of AAT data enrichment - rather than aligning data to common identifiers, PeriodO is utilised in a subsequent data enrichment stage to enrich records already indexed with named periods (such as “Bronze Age”, “Iron Age” etc.) where the dates associated with these periods are not already made explicit in the input data - providing

start/end dates to make these records comparable and searchable in the same way as other date information.

To make use of PeriodO it is first necessary to establish the reference authority in use for the named periods present in the dataset. This should be an authoritative source - such as an existing published list of period names with associated dates, or a book or other citable publication exhibiting usage of the period terms and describing the dates associated with them. A suitable reference authority may already exist within PeriodO, so the first recommended course of action is to examine the 'canonical' period list within PeriodO (i.e. the full set of curated period records) for an existing authority list a dataset might agree with. If no suitable authority list is present in the PeriodO canonical list, then a new list may be created and submitted.

3.1.3 Geographic Data

The World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84, aka EPSG:4326) is a standard geographic coordinate system (GCS), comprising a global horizontal and vertical datum and a coordinate system used (particularly by GPS systems) to express global positioning on the surface of the Earth. For ARIADNEplus purposes all spatial coordinates are to be expressed using WGS84. Other GCS also exist so coordinates in local datasets may require normalisation/transformation prior to aggregation. Use of a common GCS to express spatial information will improve opportunities for cross searching the integrated datasets.

WGS84 coordinates are expressed in degrees – the horizontal position is the longitude (having values between -180° and +180°, relative to a fixed datum of 0° at Greenwich, UK) and the vertical position is the latitude (having values between -90° and +90°, relative to a fixed datum of 0° at the equator). As an example, the global location of the Leaning Tower of Pisa (Torre di Pisa) is given by WGS84 coordinates latitude 43.723056 (43° 43' 23" N), and longitude 10.396389 (10° 23' 47" E).

WGS84 coordinates may be serialized in various machine-readable formats. In terms of the AO-Cat ontological model the coordinate values will be properties of class `AO_Spatial_Region` and its associated sub-classes: (`AO_Spatial_Region_Point`, `AO_Spatial_Region_BBox`, and `AO_Spatial_Region_Polygon`).

The AO-Cat properties 'has_latitude' and 'has_longitude' are specified with a range data type of `xsd:decimal` – so the example (in Turtle RDF format) would be expressed as:

```
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix ao: <http://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/ao/cat/> .
@prefix : <http://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/exampledata/> . #this example only

:x a ao:AO_Spatial_Region_Point ;
  rdfs:label "Location of the Leaning Tower of Pisa"@en ;
  ao:has_latitude 43.723056 ;
  ao:has_longitude 10.396389 .
```

3.2 The ARIADNEplus Aggregation Pipeline

Data providers supply their data to ARIADNE either as XML or JSON data dumps, or as an OAI-PMH feed, when regular updates may be required. For smaller data suppliers it is also possible to supply data in tabular format, for which a FastCat template can be provided.

Data is then converted into the AO Cat Ontology as RDF files and stored on the ARIADNEplus knowledge base (based on the GraphDB technology). The supplied data may already include mappings to Getty AAT or PeriodO, or these can be added to the knowledge base at this data aggregation stage.

From here the ARIADNE data resources can be re-used for multiple purposes e.g., in portals or in VREs, or by external consumers, avoiding the creation of a data silo. The knowledge base also facilitates linkage with external Linked Open Data sources, such as Wikidata.

In summary, the pipeline proceeds through the following stages:

1. Data providers get the go-ahead to proceed from the WP lead, according to the workplan. They confirm the collections to be aggregated and confirm which ARIADNE resource type they belong to.
2. Throughout the pipeline Activity Dash is used to keep track of the workflow or to communicate with the aggregation task force.
3. Providers consider if their own data schema contains all the mandatory properties of the AO-Cat.
4. Providers confirm the mechanism for data supply and frequency of update.
5. Providers work with the aggregation task force to ensure their data is mapped to the AO-Cat using the 3M mapping tool.
6. Providers work with the aggregation task force to create AAT subject mappings.
7. Providers work with the aggregation task force to create PeriodO period definitions. They can use the YearSpans tool to normalise the dates in their records, if needed.
8. Providers check spatial coordinates comply to the WGS84 spatial data standard.
9. Once notified that their dataset has been loaded to the staging portal data providers are required to check that it displays as expected and the work package lead also gives it a quality control check: <https://ariadne-portal-staging.d4science.org/>
10. The work package lead and data provider gives the go ahead to publish records on the ARIADNEplus public portal: <http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>
11. The ARIADNE communications team in WP2 work with the data providers to publicise the release of their data in the ARIADNE portal.

All support is managed either via Activity Dash or via the ARIADNEplus helpdesk in D4Science.

3.2.1 Data supplying strategies

Data providers are expected to make their metadata available so that it can be collected, transformed into the ARIADNEplus data model (AO-Cat), stored on a triplestore based on the GraphDB technology, and enriched with links to PeriodO and Getty AAT.

Figure 8 shows the data flow that will result in the availability of enriched, AO-Cat compliant metadata records in the ARIADNEplus portal.

Figure 8: The aggregation workflow applied to each set of records

3.2.2 Metadata ingestion

The ARIADNEplus aggregation system is based on the D-Net software toolkit (implemented and maintained by ISTI-CNR), which provides built-in features for collecting metadata records in different ways. The main options are:

- **OAI-PMH:** OAI-PMH is a standard protocol for metadata exchange. The aggregator can collect the whole content or only from one or more specific OAI sets. Incremental collection of records is supported if your OAI-PMH publisher supports it.
- **SFTP:** there should be one XML file per resource (i.e. not one single, big file). Incremental collection is supported. You are responsible for the SFTP server. Public key or username/password authentication modes are supported.
- **FTP(S):** there should be one XML file per resource (i.e. not one single, big file). Incremental collection is supported. You are responsible for the FTP server.
- **Dumps:** records are uploaded to a dedicated data provider folder in the ARIADNE mappings VRE.

XML files will be transformed with the 3M mapping previously defined so it is essential that the export format is the same as the one used when defining the mapping. In the case of OAI-PMH, each oai:record will be passed to the transformation. Each XML file should have one XML field containing a unique identifier. In the case of OAI-PMH, it can be the oai:identifier. The availability of a unique identifier per resource is also a requirement of the 3M mapping. Data providers must also supply a

collection level record which describes the resource as a whole. Repeated properties, such as publisher, or access rights can be cascaded from the parent collection record to all resources within that collection in the metadata enrichment phase (see 3.2.4).

3.2.3 Metadata Transformation

The aggregator automatically transforms the collected records to the ARIADNEplus data model by applying the 3M mapping defined with the X3ML mapping tool.

If the XML records already contain normalised dates, then the 3M mapping must properly map the values into AO-Cat temporal coverages. If dates are not normalised, ARIADNEplus uses a tool, called Timespans (see section, that automatically performs normalisation based on a wide set of date patterns commonly used in archaeology. The tool produces as output a modified version of the XML records, including the normalised dates.

3.2.4 Metadata Enrichment

Data providers are also required to create a mapping between their local terms and the Getty AAT using the ARIADNE Vocabulary Matching Tool, and to save it in a dedicated Matched Vocabularies folder in the D4Science ARIADNEplus mappings VRE workspace. The files are collected by the ARIADNEplus aggregator and converted into RDF by applying the 3M mapping 584.

To enrich collections with the PeriodO URIs (to fill the values in aocat:has_period), data providers need to communicate the URL of their PeriodO dataset and the criteria to match the local period terms to the PeriodO terms.

In this phase, the aggregation manager can also apply some patches to the aggregated data. Examples are the addition of default values to properties and propagation of properties from the collection level record to its individual resources (e.g. the publisher or the access right is provided only at the level of the collection record but it applies by default to all its resources).

4 Tools for supporting data integration

4.1 The 3M Mapping Tool

The X3ML Toolkit is a set of small, open source, microservices that follow the SYNERGY Reference Model⁶ of data provision and aggregation. They are designed with open interfaces and they can be easily customised and adapted to complex environments. The key components of the toolkit are:

- Mapping Memory Manager - 3M is a tool for managing mapping definition files. It provides a number of administrative actions that assist the data supplying partners manage their mapping definition files.
- 3M Editor - is the interface tool that allows the domain experts to build mappings. It provides:
 - Source and target agnostic mapping facility
 - Guided mapping according to deployed ontology's logic
 - Comment and justification facility
 - Mapping storage
 - Separated instance generation practice for IT professionals
- X3ML Engine - The X3ML Engine realises the transformation of the source records to the target format. The engine takes as input the source data (currently in the form of an XML document), the description of the mappings in the X3ML mapping definition file and the URI generation policy file and is responsible for transforming the source document into a valid RDF document which corresponds to the input XML file, with respect to the given mappings and policy.
- RDF visualizer – The visualizer allows a fast way to inspect the transformed records.

The X3ML Toolkit is deployed for ARIADNEplus on D4 science at:

https://ariadne.d4science.org/group/ariadneplus_mappings/mapping-tool

Figure 9: The workflow of the X3ML Toolkit

⁶ <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/Resources/the-synergy-reference-model-of-data-provision-and-aggregation>

Partners are encouraged to undertake their own 3M mapping, for which they can consult the detailed help guide in the aggregation pipeline user guide, Nonetheless, our experience has suggested that this can be a daunting task for archaeological data providers and the aggregation team has supported this stage of the workflow.

4.1.1 New & Improved 3M

3M is a web tool aiming at assisting end-users to easily complete the definition process, by providing the appropriate environment that offers rich and complex functionality hidden under a simple and friendly user interface. It allows data experts to transform their internal structured data and other associated contextual knowledge to other schemata, including the CIDOC CRM (Conceptual Reference Model). Fields or elements from a source database (Source Nodes) are aligned with one or more entities described in the target schema so that the data from an entire system can be transformed. The purpose of this is typically their integration with other data also transformed to the same target schema.

The screenshot displays the 3M workspace environment. At the top, there is a blue header with the 3M logo, the user name 'Vangelis Kriostakis', and project information: 'ARIADNEplus Excavation m...'. Below the header, there are several icons for actions like 'Validate Selections', 'Compact View', and 'Completed'. The main workspace is titled 'Mapping #1 - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)'. It is divided into three sections:

- Domain:** Shows a 'Source Node: //ExcavationUnit' and a 'Target Entity: A1_Excavation_Process_Unit' with properties like 'AO_Individual_Data_Resource', 'Constant: Workshop', 'TwoLevelCustomURI', 'CompositeLabel', and 'PPP_Excavation_Unit'. A 'Relation: is_part_of' is also defined with 'Entity: AO_Collection' and 'Constant: Workshop'.
- Link #1:** Shows a 'Source Relation: ExcavationInfo/ExcavationWork' and a 'Target Relation: P33_used_specific_technique'. It includes 'Target Entity: E29_Design_or_Procedure' with properties like 'dp1', 'OneLevelCustomURI', 'CompositeLabel', and 'P2_has_type'.
- Link #2:** Shows a 'Source Relation: ExcavationInfo/ExcavationTechnique' and a 'Target Relation: P33_used_specific_technique'. It includes 'Target Entity: E55_Type' with properties like 'ConceptURI-2', 'Concept', 'prefLabel', and 'text: text(), language: gr'.

Figure 10: Workspace environment of 3M

A new redesigned 3M version has been developed, offering several improvements over the old one. The goal and objectives remain the same; however, extra effort has been made into making it more useful, robust and responsive for end users. The following list highlights some of the main improvements / additions:

- Powered by new technologies (React, Java Spring, Material Design, etc.);
- Better performance stability over the old 3M;
- New improved and modern UI, which is configurable in several aspects;
- Allows users to organise mappings by labelling them under categories;

- Encapsulates a generator definition manager;
 - Allows construction and use of new definitions;
 - Allows addition of further definitions from a generator policy file;
 - Allows export of the definitions used to a new generator policy file;
 - Provides steps for recovering issues related to missing definitions within a mapping;
- Prevents users from defining the same namespaces with different prefixes;
- Provides validation of all selected values (uncovering conflicts);
- Supports the use of native additional elements;
- Support the usage of named graphs within Mapping, Domain and Link Elements;
- Allows multiple users to edit the same mapping simultaneously, by automatically handling the synchronisation among the different user views;
- Provides a way of keeping track of the progress made, based on the source input values coverage;
- Better supports the RDF Visualizer by providing a list of the instances by class.

4.2 The FastCat tool

FastCat is an innovative tool designed for archaeologists, historians and other cultural heritage researchers who need to manually digitise structured and semi-structured historical documents in a fast and accurate way, in order to create their research dataset. It combines ease of use and quick data entry of the classic spreadsheet functionality, with the information accuracy typically associated with a complex (public) database. This is accomplished through data entry templates, which are designed to mirror the structure and data entry logic of the original data source, in the digital space. A feature that makes FastCat stand out from traditional spreadsheet tools is that it can natively hold data tables within other data tables, which is very useful for recording archaeological data sources.

An ARIADNEplus resource catalogue template has been defined and implemented following the AO-Cat ontology. It provides an easy way for data providers whose data does not follow a pre-defined schema to upload relatively small amounts of data into the ARIADNE knowledge base.

The screenshot shows the FastCat interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the 'Fast Cat' logo and a search icon. Below this is a header for 'Catalogue of Resources, ADS, Maria Theodoridou'. The main content area is divided into two sections:

FastCat Record Information

Use english to fill in the fields of this table

Id	Creation date	Date		Authors		
		Last Modified	Name *	Surname *	Provider	
5	2020-05-12	2020-05-14T14:26:44	Maria	Theodoridou	ADS	

Catalogue of Resources

* indicates a mandatory field

	has_original_id	has_title	has_description	has_ARIADNE_subject	has_native_subject	has_language	was_created_on	has_landing_page	has_access_policy	has_access_rights
	* Original ID	* Title	Description	* ARIADNE subject	* Native subject	* Language	* Created On	Landing Page	Access Policy	* Access Rights
1	1000398			Site/monument						
2	1001785			Site/monument						
3	1001786			Site/monument						
4	1001787			Site/monument						
5	1001788			Site/monument						
6	1000324			Site/monument						
7	1001054			Site/monument						
8	1000272			Fieldwork						
9	1000272m			Site/monument						
10	1000304			Site/monument						
11	1000003			Fieldwork						
12	1001957			Site/monument						
13	1000801			Site/monument						
14	1001970			Site/monument						

At the bottom of the interface, there is a footer with 'Terms of Use | Privacy Policy | © 2019-2020 FORTH-ICS CCI' on the left and 'System version 2.6-SNAPSHOT (2020-01-22T20:00) --- Database: Dev_dev' on the right.

Figure 11: FastCat used to assign ARIADNE_subject to all ADS collections.

FastCat is also an easy way to familiarise data providers with the classes of AO-Cat and their use. Each data provider can map a few sample records from their collections to the AO-Cat and see how they are presented in the ARIADNEplus cloud.

4.3 The Vocabulary Matching Tool

To facilitate the production of mappings from local subject vocabularies to the Getty AAT ARIADNE has provided a Vocabulary Matching Tool (VMT).⁷ The VMT is a browser-based application with no user installation or configuration requirements. It has a multilingual user interface – the current UI languages supported are German, English, Spanish, French, Italian and Dutch. Rather than performing automated syntactic matching based on textual labels alone, users instead search and browse the AAT, viewing the hierarchical context and scope of concepts to make a better-informed match.

⁷ <https://vmt.ariadne.d4science.org/vmt/>

Vocabulary Matching Tool

English

Source Concept	Match Type	Target Concept	Suggest	Delete Row
Identifier		Filter column...		
Abbey Church	Close Match	abbey churches	🔍	🗑️
ABBEY	Exact Match	abbeys (monasteries)	🔍	🗑️
AGRICULTURAL BUILDING	Exact Match	agricultural buildings	🔍	🗑️
AGRICULTURAL DWELLING	Broad Match	agricultural buildings	🔍	🗑️
AGRICULTURAL HALL	Broad Match	agricultural buildings	🔍	🗑️
FARM BUILDING	Close Match	agricultural buildings	🔍	🗑️
FIELD SYSTEM	Broad Match	agricultural land	🔍	🗑️
FIELD SYSTEM	Broad Match	agricultural land	🔍	🗑️
LAND USE SITE	Broad Match	agricultural land	🔍	🗑️
LYNCHET	Broad Match	agricultural land	🔍	🗑️
CURVILINEAR ENCLOSURE	Broad Match	agricultural settlements	🔍	🗑️
DITCHED ENCLOSURE	Broad Match	agricultural settlements	🔍	🗑️
DOUBLE DITCHED ENCLOSURE	Broad Match	agricultural settlements	🔍	🗑️
ENCLOSED SETTLEMENT	Broad Match	agricultural settlements	🔍	🗑️
ENCLOSURE	Broad Match	agricultural settlements	🔍	🗑️
AGRICULTURE AND SUBSISTENCE	Broad Match	agriculture	🔍	🗑️
AIR RAID SHELTER	Exact Match	air raid shelters	🔍	🗑️
AIRCRAFT	Close Match	aircraft	🔍	🗑️

390 rows

IMPORT JSON EXPORT JSON EXPORT CSV + ADD NEW ROW CLEAR ROWS SHOW HELP

ARIADNEplus
Created by University of South Wales

ARIADNEplus is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No 823914)

This application retrieves some information originating from Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)® which is made available under the ODC Attribution License. See <http://vocab.getty.edu/> for further details.

Figure 12: The Vocabulary Matching Tool

Usually, users will just make one match from any given local concept to an AAT concept - having mapped to an AAT target concept there is no need for additional mappings to narrower AAT concepts. However, the application does also support the creation of both one-to-many and many-to-one mappings. The local source concept may be a composite or pre-coordinated concept related to multiple genuinely different AAT concepts e.g. “bronze spearheads”. In this case, two mappings can be made – firstly to aat:300010957 “bronze (metal)” and secondly to aat:300037118 “spearheads”.

The type of match between the source concept and the target concept will be one of the possible SKOS mapping properties as defined by the SKOS reference document⁸, listed here in order of preference:

- **Exact Match** - this match type indicates that there is "a high degree of confidence that the concepts can be used interchangeably across a wide range of information retrieval applications".

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/#mapping>

- **Close Match** - can be used to link concepts "*that are sufficiently similar that they can be used interchangeably in some information retrieval applications*". It is a more approximate type of relationship between the source and target concepts.
- **Broad Match** - expresses a hierarchical generic relationship between concepts. If a source concept is more specific in scope than any AAT available concept, then one can make a Broad Match link to the AAT concept. This is useful for cases when a source vocabulary contains concepts that are more detailed. In this case the "all/some" rule should hold true e.g. "coffee cups" skos:broadMatch "cups" - ALL coffee cups are cups; SOME cups are coffee cups.
- **Narrow Match** - expresses a hierarchical generic relationship between concepts. It is not expected that users would make much use of Narrow Match relationships for ARIADNEplus vocabularies. The "some/all" rule should hold true e.g. "cups" skos:narrowMatch "coffee cups" - SOME cups are coffee cups; ALL coffee cups are cups.
- **Related Match** - expresses an associative relationship between concepts. The exact nature of the relationship is not explicitly spelled out, only that there is some connection between them e.g. bullets skos:relatedMatch guns. Bullets are associated with guns, although this relationship is different to the other relationship types listed. Preferably users would aim to create a more direct concept mapping wherever the target AAT vocabulary supports it (in this case skos:exactMatch aat:300201694 "bullets").
- Once created the sets of mappings are exported from the VMT and deposited on D4 Science for use in the data enrichment processing.

4.4 The YearSpans tool

Archaeological dataset records often give a textual expression of dating rather than absolute numeric years for the dating of artefacts. These textual data values may be expressed in a variety of formats, also in different languages. There can be prefixes present such as 'Circa', 'Early', 'Mid', 'Late' - and suffixes such as 'A.D.', 'C.E.', 'B.C.', 'B.C.E.', 'B.P.' that may influence the dates intended. This can present a data integration issue, as illustrated in the table below:

Type	Language	Input	Min	Max
Ordinal named / numbered century	English	Circa Second Century BC	-200	-101
	English	Eleventh Century CE	1001	1100
	Dutch	11e eeuw na Christus	1001	1100
	French	XIe siècle après JC	1001	1100
	German	11. Jahrhundert n. Chr	1001	1100
	Spanish	siglo XI d.C.	1001	1100
	Norwegian	1100-tallet e.Kr.	1001	1100
	Swedish	elfte århundrade e.Kr.	1001	1100
	Italian	XI secolo d.C.	1001	1100
	Italian	intorno a VI sec. d.C.	501	600
Year span	English	1450-1460	1450	1460
	English	1485-86	1485	1486
Single year	English	C. 1485	1485	1485

Type	Language	Input	Min	Max
(with tolerance)	English	1540±9	1531	1549
	English	AD400+	400	400
	English	400 AD	400	400
Decade	English	Circa 1860s	1860	1869
	Italian	intorno al decennio 1910	1910	1919
Century span	English	5th – 6th century AD	401	600
	Italian	VIII-VII secolo a.C.	-800	-601
Month and year	English	July 1855	1855	1855
	Italian	Luglio 1855	1855	1855
Season and year	English	Summer 1855	1855	1855
	Italian	Estate 1855	1855	1855
Named periods (from lookup)	English	Georgian	1714	1837
	English	Victorian	1837	1901

Figure 13: Various ways to express year spans

Normalising this data can make later search and comparison of the records easier and more accurate. We can do this by supplementing the original values with additional attributes defining the start and end years of the year span. This application attempts to match textual values representing year spans to a number of (language-specific) known patterns, and from there to derive the intended start/end years of the year span. For some cases the start/end years are present and can be extracted directly from the textual string, however in most cases a degree of additional interpretation and processing is required after the initial pattern match is made. The output facilitates logical comparison of textual year spans as often expressed in datasets. Due to the wide variety of potential formats (including punctuation and spurious extra text or white space), the matching patterns developed cannot comprehensively cater for every possible free-text variation present, so any remaining records not processed by this initial automated method can be manually reviewed and assigned suitable start/end years.⁹

4.5 The Activity Dash tool

Activity Dash is an online web application, accessed through any modern web browser, which helps organise and track workflows with respect to their several processes (activities). As soon as data providers are given the go ahead to proceed a dedicated workflow is set up by the sub-task leader. End users of the system are capable of observing the progress developed under one or more workflows and updating it, when required. In general, the application combines:

- i. A workflow manager and tracker;
- ii. A collaborative environment;
- iii. A notification means for stakeholders;
- iv. A reference point for stakeholders, to watch the progress done on workflows.

⁹ <https://github.com/cbinding/years spans>

All workflows within the system are grouped by projects, where access is regulated by user groups, defined by some project owner user. Following the same pattern, each workflow within a project has its own user group defined by the workflow owner.

Figure 14: The Activity Dash application

The workspace environment offered by the system, presents the workflow as divided in activities, which are further divided in tasks. The workflow owner, assigns users to activities, and each activity assignee, assigns other users to tasks. All stakeholder users can simultaneously edit or extend the workflow, without worrying about missing potential changes being made by others on their shared workspace. This is mainly achieved, due to systems capability of syncing the shared workspace view, among all users behind different browsers.

Activities within the workflow are capable of holding associations between others. This is mainly done when some activity depends on the completeness of other activities. The same can also be applied for tasks, always within the same activity. The system is capable of automatically informing stakeholders, under specific circumstances, about the completeness of some activity and any new activity or task assignment or dismissal.

4.6 The Helpdesk tool

As ARIADNEplus is a collaborative initiative with multiple participants representing varying levels of experience, it was important to assist content providers in a more structured way in all phases of their data contribution. Based on earlier experiences from the ARIADNE project, as well as other projects, it was decided that a ticketing service was needed where it is possible to offer efficient interaction

with specialist teams of experts, and where one could track/document and follow up issues reported by participating members. In the D4Science infrastructure it is possible to implement the issue tracking system called “Redmine”. Redmine was selected because it integrates perfectly into the D4Science infrastructure, and provides seamless and transparent access to the Redmine Helpdesk project with no need for further login.

Redmine is a web-based project management and issue tracking tool. Within Redmine it is possible to create, update, track, and resolve reported issues, while providing assistance at every stage of the process, from preparation to the definition of mappings, up to fine-tuning the data harvesting and data acquisition mechanisms within the ARIADNEplus infrastructure. In addition to the tracking system, it supports flexible role-based access control (to support the roles of the different users); Gantt charts provide visual representations of the project deadlines, linked to calendar; e-mail notifications and a wiki.

The service is up and running, allowing content providers to contact the right expert group, accelerating the process to find solutions. Additional benefits include fostering collaborations, and working as a future knowledge base with solutions to common problems and other information. The Helpdesk is primarily to be used if participants have queries to be resolved, features to request, suggestions, and bugs to report. When entering the Helpdesk area there is an overview with information on how to use the system, for example the mandatory choice between Bug, Feature, and Support in the tracker field. Users must add information in the Subject and Description fields. The Category field is also mandatory, and allows users to choose between several areas described below. Choosing a category ensures the issue reaches the correct specialist team of experts.

5 Status of the integration

This section reports on progress made on the integration of data and metadata provided by the ARIADNEplus archaeological data suppliers to date. We also anticipate the remaining datasets expected to be integrated during the final four months of activity, although it is expected that the process of adding new collections and updating existing collections will also continue beyond the end of the current funded project, using the workflow established.

Throughout the project integration has been managed by an aggregation task force of core partners involved in Work Packages 4 and 5. This has met online on average every 2-3 weeks throughout the project, and on some 40 occasions, with further work conducted between meetings via the Helpdesk and ActivityDash.

5.1 Aggregation Priorities

Prioritisation was guided by five criteria:

1. Ease of mapping and capacity to build upon lessons learned in ARIADNE.
2. Potential to aggregate a large number of records. Initial analysis of datasets which partners were able to supply indicated that over two million records would be available for aggregation, and in the first 18 months we prioritised large collections with rich and high-quality metadata from established repositories (DANS, SND, ADS) to give us examples to showcase to users and to provide the portal developers in WP12 with a critical mass of high-quality data to use as test data in portal development.
3. The fact that these datasets correspond well with the “What”, “When”, “Where” parameters which have steered the development of the portal interface, and can be made interoperable by mappings to the Getty AAT (for “What”), option of Period search (for “When”), and adherence to WGS 84 (for “Where”).
4. The fact that most partners had some datasets which fell into one or more of these parameters, and would therefore gain experience of the mapping process, and have some data visible in the portal by the end of the project.
5. User needs. Priorities were also guided by the User Needs Survey conducted by SRFG in the first nine months of the project (Deliverable 2.1).

We were also conscious that a Big Data approach which allowed researchers to visualise and interrogate large data sets could help address some of the grand challenge research questions in Archaeology.

5.2 Current status of data integration

We are able to report outstanding success in achieving a critical mass of high-quality archaeological data resources, available for research under an open licence, and easily discoverable via the ARIADNE portal, which represents a powerful research tool in its own right. As this Deliverable is submitted, we have over 3.2 million resources integrated in the portal. These derive from over 30 Partner data providers (or “Publishers”) from as many countries, and covering three continents. We anticipate that

by Month 48 over 40 data providers will be represented. Most significantly this includes data from over ten Associate Partners who have asked to supply data at their own expense, but with support of the ARIADNE Aggregation Task Force. These include the existing specialist multinational aggregation services ROCEEH and THANADOS, as well as some prestigious national institutions such as the British Museum. There is a clear appreciation of the importance of ARIADNE amongst the world archaeological community and an appetite from those beyond the original project partnership to make their data sets available via the ARIADNE platform.

5.2.1 Resources

At the time of submission of this deliverable dataset integration is still in progress and will continue until the end of the funded project, and likely beyond. Therefore, this report includes a Month 44 snapshot of data published in the public portal, as well as that which is under review in the staging portal.¹⁰ There are multiple attributes by which resources can be filtered, but a numeric listing by ARIADNE resource types demonstrates the wide range of datasets which have been successfully rendered interoperable by the AO-Cat model.

Site/monument	1,173,549
Fieldwork	393,919
Fieldwork report	276,803
Fieldwork archive	113,180
Building survey	649
Maritime	33,421
Burial	11,537
Rock Art	26,803
Inscription	83,347
Artefact	537,180
Coin	470,788
Scientific Analysis	7,785
Date	7,725
TOTAL	3,136,686

¹⁰ <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>
<https://ariadne-portal-staging.d4science.org/>

5.2.1.1 Partners

Almost all archaeological partners have provided data for integration. The number of resources can be misleading as one resource may reflect a single affect record or a major research database, but they give an indication of the reach and significance of ARIADNEplus. The table below reflects the anticipated position at M48; italicised figures are estimates at M44.

Archaeology Data Service	UK	<i>1,100,000</i>
CONICET	Argentina	2502
OEAW	Austria	<i>500</i>
BUP	Belgium	<i>5000</i>
NIAM-BAS	Bulgaria	<i>1000</i>
Cyprus Institute	Cyprus	<i>2000</i>
Archaeological Institute of Zagreb	Croatia	<i>500</i>
ARUP: AIS-CR	Czech Republic	229999
Aarhus University	Denmark	8687
Helsinki University	Finland	<i>1000</i>
CNRS	France	10
INRAP	France	38073
RGK	Germany	<i>20000</i>
Patras University	Greece	3
Hungarian National Museum	Hungary	59686
Fornleifastofnun Islands	Iceland	<i>2000</i>
CARARE	Ireland	<i>15000</i>
Israel Antiquities Authority	Israel	<i>1000</i>
AIAC	Italy	14360
INFN	Italy	43
ICCU	Italy	<i>2000</i>
Nara Research Institute	Japan	141159

DANS-KNAW	Netherlands	100355
National Historical Museum	Norway	860000
LNEC	Portugal	1000
INP	Romania	18279
IAMP	Romania	200
ZRC-SAZU	Slovenia	8911
CENIEH	Spain	8405
University of Barcelona	Spain	57089
SND	Sweden	484
tDAR	United States	180

5.2.1.2 Associate Partners

As noted above, ARIADNE has drawn interest from many organisations beyond the original consortium. Some have joined as associate partners, data for other organisations has been brokered via existing partners. The data has been prepared for integration at their own expense, but with support from the aggregation task force.

ROCEEH	Germany	7537
THANADOS	Germany	10000
British School in Athens	Greece	500
French School in Athens	Greece	500
British School in Ankara	Turkey	8
Innsbruck University	Austria	50
Serbian Academy of Arts and Sciences	Serbia	100
British Museum (via ADS)	United Kingdom	946901
Historic Environment Scotland (via ADS)	United Kingdom	334636
SEAD (via SND)	Sweden	10000
Swedish Rock Art project (via SND)	Sweden	25223

DCCD (Via DANS)	Netherlands	10000
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5.2.2 AO-Cat mappings

Each provider submits for aggregation one or more collections. Each collection requires a mapping to the AO-Cat, generally using the 3M tool, although where Fast-Cat has been adopted there is a single Fast-Cat 3M mapping to streamline the process. For other partners we have tried to minimise the proliferation of mappings, to avoid redundancy and the creation of overheads for sustainability, because if the AO-Cat is modified, the mappings will also need to be updated. For example, at one stage there were over ten different mappings to cover the range of UoY-ADS datasets, which we have reduced to five.

As of August 1, 2022 the following mappings have been implemented in 3M:

Resource	Mapping
Archaeology Data Service (ADS)	
Generic mapping covering the majority of ADS collections	591
Archaeology Data Service Grey Literature, unpublished reports from fieldwork.	674
ADS Archives Collection, comprises individual research project and fieldwork digital archives preserved by the Archaeology Data Service, and made available for re-use under an Open Licence.	713
Historic Environment Scotland (HES) CANMORE database, more than 320,000 records and 1.3 million catalogue entries for archaeological sites, buildings, industry and maritime heritage across Scotland.	959
British Museum Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS) Artefacts, records of archaeological finds discovered by members of the public. These are found while carrying out a wide range of activities including metal-detecting.	941
British Museum Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS) Coins, records of the Oxford University Celtic Coin Index (CCI- prefix) and Cardiff University's Iron Age and Roman coins of Wales project (IARCW- prefix).	943
Auxiliary mapping for ADS native subjects to AAT	584
Auxiliary mapping assigning ARIADNE_subjects to all ADS collections	623
Auxiliary mapping of the ADS temporal subjects to PeriodO	586
HNM	
Hungarian National Museum Archaeology database with fundamental information on archaeological sites and documentations of the sites.	608

International Association for Classical Archaeology (AIAC)	
Fasti Online, a database of excavations since 2000.	614
Fasti Online update	729
Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	
EASY, DANS' online archiving (deposit, preservation and reuse) service. A wealth of digital archaeological excavation data such as maps, field drawings, photographs, tables and publications. PAN, the long-term preservation of the finds of the Portable Antiquities of the Netherlands	658
Example on how to use native subjects already mapped to Narcis	618
Swedish National Data Service (SND)	
Swedish National Data Service Online Catalogue, a detailed description of all studies in SND's collection. Information on sample, data collection methodology, related studies and publications.	593
SHFA image archive, with more than 20,000 digitized images of rock carving documentation, primarily from Sweden but also from Denmark, Norway, Italy and Spain.	590
Archaeological Information System of the Czech Republic (AIS CR)	
AMCR, Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic.	661
CENIEH	
Archaeological Site's collection, 11 archaeopaleontological excavations carried out during the year 2020 and directed by different CENIEH researchers.	916
Cenieh Institutional Repository (CIR) - Fieldwork reports.	635
Atapuerca Sediment Collection, more than 7000 records generated from the database of sediment samples excavated from some Pleistocene and Holocene sites of the Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain).	917
IDACOR (CONICET/UNC)	
BADACOR collection, Archaeological Database of Córdoba. Contains descriptions of archaeological sites from data generated through surveys, administrative records, collection records, and archaeological excavations.	797
Alemandri collection of lithic and ceramic, archaeological and ethnographic objects from Argentine Patagonia.	970

Aarhus University	
DIME collection, find records from the Danish recording portal for archaeological finds produced by members of the public. It consists of over 100.000 records of portable antiquities.	697
German Archaeological Institute (DAI)	
AFE-RGK coin collection, the coin find database of the Roman-Germanic Commission (RGK) of the German Archaeological Institute (DAI)	954
Institute of Archaeology Vasile Parvan (IAVP)	
Muslim Ottoman sites and monuments in Dobruja	724
Communist agricultural system traces in Dobruja	921
INFN	
43 collections of scientific data (radiocarbon dating, isotope analysis, X-ray radiography etc.) provided via FastCat	738
Institut national de recherches archéologiques préventives (Inrap)	
Dolia, bibliographical references of operation reports and works kept in Inrap's documentation centres.	643
Laboratório nacional de engenharia civil (LNEC)	
DB-HERITAGE, System for systematic data recording relating to the history, properties and performance of construction materials aimed for improving knowledge for the conservation and restoration of heritage and historical structures.	852
ICCD - Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione	
22 collections on archaeological finds in Italy.	877
NARA National Research Institute for Cultural Properties	
NABUNKEN, Comprehensive Database of Archaeological Site Reports Japan	739
OEAW	
ARCHES	844
The Cyprus Institute (Cyl)	
Cypriot Medieval Coins Collection, digital library dedicated to the study, promotion and dissemination of the history of Medieval Cypriot Coinage	891
Epigraphies	911
Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities	

ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD), information about more than 1800 sites and 10,000 assemblages, based on a review of over 2800 articles, books, theses, and reports written in many languages	696
THANADOS	
THANADOS, the Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures.	945
University of Barcelona	
CEIPAC- Corpus de epigrafia anfórica latina, collection of seals, picti titles and graffiti on Roman amphorae,	971
ZRC-SAZU	
ARKAS (Archaeological Cadastre of Slovenia), database of archaeological sites in Slovenia.	642
Zbiva, archaeological database for eastern Alps and its surrounding regions in the early Middle Ages. It is focused on the sites in Slovenia, Austria, on the NW Croatian coast, and in the NE regions in Italy.	698
National Institute of Archaeology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NIAM-BAS)	
AIS AKB, Archaeological information system for registered archaeological sites in Bulgaria	657
National Heritage Institute - Romania (INP)	
Romanian National Archaeological Record (Repertoriul Arheologic Național - RAN), the official recording of all the sites, areas and archaeological findings in Romania	876
British School of Athens	
Excavation Project collection	950
tDAR	
Casa Grande Ruins National Monument collection	906, 976
FastCat	
Several top level collections created via FastCat records	714, 892

5.3 Final priorities

In the upcoming final stages of the funded project, we will prioritise datasets which are already being prepared for integration, maximising the international coverage and representation of all partners. There are also several partners who provided data early in the project who wish to take the opportunity to update and enhance their data supply.

But we will also promote to all data providers how the portal interface can be used to provide a partner, or national, view of the data integrated to this point. This has already been previewed in the Publisher landing pages, but we anticipate it is an attractive feature for all data provider websites.¹¹ It has also become clear that the ARIADNE resource type is a powerful feature that allows thematic views of the ARIADNE knowledge base. For example, in the UK, the ADS has adopted the AO-Cat with few modifications as a data model for integration of all UK maritime heritage data, in a project which forms part of the UK's Towards a National Collection programme.¹² ADS will create an instance of the ARIADNE portal, hard-wired to display only resources which have been tagged as maritime, to demonstrate a UK marine view of the ARIADNE triplestore. Hence, the ontology and infrastructure developed and implemented in ARIADNEplus can be demonstrated to offer an extensible and flexible resource for data integration at an international, national and thematic level, providing multiple showcases for the same resources tailored for multiple audiences.

¹¹e.g. [https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/publisher/inrap?publisher=Institut%20national%20de%20recherches%20archéologiques%20préventives%20\(Inrap\)](https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/publisher/inrap?publisher=Institut%20national%20de%20recherches%20archéologiques%20préventives%20(Inrap))

¹² <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/>

6 Digital Libraries Integration

This section presents an update on the activities related to Task 4.5, “Integrating archaeological digital libraries with ARIADNEplus” which are aimed at linking the ARIADNEplus data space with repositories of scientific publications, to establish links between the archaeological data in ARIADNEplus and the information present in external digital libraries. This is implemented by exploiting OpenAIRE and its open access digital archives and the links to individual journals such as “Internet Archaeology” or “Archeologia e Calcolatori”.

The update follows what was reported in section 7 of D4.1, “Initial report on dataset integration”, (with the same title as this section). In D4.1, the reader can find information about OpenAIRE¹³ and the relevant gateway for *Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage*. Since then, the gateway and its configuration have been updated, and it has been moved from Beta to Production, available here: <https://dh-ch.openaire.eu>. Below, we will instead focus on the work for linking ARIADNEplus to OpenAIRE publications. We will describe the methodology used with the text mining relational citation matching algorithm we developed, and the results produced.

We started by downloading the complete ARIADNE graph from the SPARQL endpoint at <https://graphdb.ariadne.d4science.org/sparql> and imported searchable predicates into a relational database table. Such predicates were the following:

- id,
- title,
- ariadne_subjects,
- publisher,
- creators,
- owners,
- contributors,
- native_subjects,
- types,
- create_year,
- landingpageurl, and
- issuedate.

The produced table contained 2.127.626 distinct records. We cleaned the table to exclude “dirty” records (e.g., with non-descriptive titles and metadata). For example record <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/F1550EDE-8C8C-34C4-AECF-BF784E9FBFF5> has the title “X Y Z” which is prone to many false positives. Similarly, resource <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/AB84BA58-BE34-345B-AAEF-51CF849359D4> has the title “A very large number of...”.

¹³ www.openaire.eu

We first searched the full-texts of OpenAIRE publication for occurrences of URLs, which are usually DOIs, but could also be ISBN or other identifiers. We also matched this table against the OpenAIRE metadata using our citation matching algorithm available at <https://github.com/madgik/recital>.

The algorithm ran successfully and produced 33,683 results. From these, we identified 5,871 high confidence links from OpenAIRE publications to ARIADNE records. Moreover, there are 13,500 with medium confidence. We are currently validating these records. The remaining links are low confidence links which are considered to be false positives. Most of these false positives were produced due to some very common titles that are used in several ARIADNE records. For example, there are titles like the following:

- *“London Hospital Medical College”* (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/D7AF7E99-384F-3313-A817-1387CE2CFD80>)
- *“Nationwide Building Society”* (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/522D76E9-4087-30B9-84E8-C67D0BABA292>)
- *“Oxford University Press”* (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/76D5978A-BCE2-3ED4-AFD1-00D84EB9FC98>)
- *“The Royal Institution”* (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/E8841D30-8EE1-33D3-B011-6E2F26A07646>)
- *“The university of Greenwich”* (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Resource/273EBC07-5D4F-3E6C-8AA6-28D2F63AD806>)

These titles are frequently encountered in the full-texts of publications as false positives, but are given low confidence values by our algorithm, as they do not contain enough additional metadata that could also be matched.

Until the end of the project, our plan is to complete curating the remaining 13.5K links (a manual, time-consuming task), in order to optimise the confidence threshold for our algorithm. This means that the results of the algorithm will be filtered, so that only links with confidence over this threshold will be outputted as valid links; the rest will be discarded. Setting this threshold usually requires a trade-off between precision and recall. Our strategy will be to favour high precision over high recall. In other words, we prefer that the results of our algorithm are correct, even if it means sacrificing some valid links with medium confidence.

However, as a by-product of the curation and threshold setting process, ARIADNEplus records with dirty titles or other incorrect metadata are being identified (like the example given above), providing valuable data cleaning feedback for ARIADNEplus metadata.

Finally, the curated mining module output will be integrated, enhancing the ARIADNEplus triplestore.

7 Conclusions

In conclusion, all the activities of WP4 have contributed significantly to the integration of the archaeological datasets in ARIADNEplus. The AO-Cat model was the most remarkable result of these activities as its development benefited from the contribution of all partners and highlighted the excellent synergy between them. The definition of this standard has made it possible to achieve an excellent level of integration. The mapping, enrichment and conversion tools specifically created for this purpose have played an important role in assisting content providers in all phases of the preparation and contribution of their datasets. The use of the Helpdesk also simplified communication between information scientists and content providers.

ARIADNEplus has been outstandingly successful in bringing together a much broader range of records than the predecessor ARIADNE project, upon whose success it has been able to build. The intention was to integrate datasets ranging widely in space and time, and across a wider range of archaeological sub-domains. At Month 44 we have over 1120 resources which pre-date 1,000,000 BP, and 62,723 resources which post-date AD 1900, demonstrating the full range of 21st century archaeological research. We have resources from North and South America, Europe and Scandinavia, and Asia. The integrated data covers every ARIADNE resource type, from inscriptions and rock art to scientific analyses and dating resources. We already provide access to over 3 million resources in total, and anticipate that by month 48 that figure will have reached some 4 million resources. We have integrated over one million records for individual sites and monuments, over 500,000 artefacts and 450,000 coins. Our catalogue includes over 250,000 unpublished fieldwork reports, and over 100,000 full fieldwork archives. These represent a massive digital research infrastructure now available freely and easily as Open Access data to European scientists and researchers, teachers and students, as well as to interested members of the public.

Significant progress has also been made on the integration of the ARIADNEplus data space with repositories of scientific publications, to establish links between the archaeological data in ARIADNEplus and the information present in external digital libraries. The use of advanced text mining tools and the new methodologies implemented through the improved relational citation matching algorithm of the gateway for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage has made this activity particularly effective.

The data integration achieved in WP4 has created a tremendously powerful research infrastructure. For those familiar with SPARQL the triplestore can be queried directly, and the ARIADNE Knowledge Base can also be linked to other Linked Open Data Resources, for example in numismatics. However, the ARIADNE portal is a powerful research tool in its own right. For example, the timeline temporal browser can be used to understand the temporal range of specific artefact types in different regions of the world. The map-based view can be used to visualise the spread of various forms of material culture. Thus, the portal can be used, to give just one example, to bring together artefactual data from multiple countries to examine issues of migration in prehistory or early history. It also allows the linkage of distributions of isolated finds of artefacts with those from excavated sites, and with scientific dating and analyses. To this point, such datasets have often been stored in independent silos, hampering research. ARIADNE has allowed their integration. For the UK, for example, the ARIADNE

portal is the first time that data from the national scheme for the public recording of finds, the Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS), can be searched alongside data from the state national records for sites and monuments, and with over 60,000 unpublished fieldwork reports made available via the Archaeology Data Service. The PAS can also now be cross-searched with equivalent public datasets from other countries, including DIME from Denmark, PAN from the Netherlands, and FindSampo from Finland. This is important, not just as it demonstrates the value of Citizen Science (as explored in WP16) but because most big research questions transcend modern political boundaries, and ARIADNE directly responds to this scientific challenge.

The interest shown in ARIADNE, and the enthusiasm of additional organisations to join, bodes well for sustainability. Several major repositories, including SND in Sweden and ADS in the UK have included use of the data integration provided by the portal infrastructure, of installations of parts of it, within their own strategic planning and we are now developing business plans to facilitate ongoing support, both for updating existing resources, and for adding new ones.